

**ANTH-170-52: From Artifacts to Arguments:
Introduction to the Archaeology of Prehistoric Europe**

Time: MW: 12:00–1:15
Location: BH 101
Email: jessicabeck@vassar.edu
Office Hours: M: 2:00–4:00
BH 312

“Graffiti Removal” by Banksy

How did humans survive during the last Ice Age? Who is responsible for the cave paintings of Lascaux? What exactly is a henge? In this course, we will explore the answers to these questions and more, covering topics ranging from ancient subsistence systems to exchange networks, mortuary practices, and technology.

The class is divided into four units: (1) Introduction to Archaeological Theory and History; (2) The Paleolithic; (3) The Neolithic; (4) The Copper Age–Bronze Age. Students will learn to evaluate archaeological evidence, assess the importance of theory in reconstructing prehistoric lifeways, and identify key sites, archaeologists, and artifacts in European prehistory. In addition to painting a portrait of the economies, exchange networks, social organization and ritual practices of early European communities, this course also emphasizes the utility of different archaeological lines of evidence, describing the complementary information that can be recovered from lithics, ceramics, animal bones, human bones and ancient plant remains.

Over the course of the seminar, students will learn how to formulate clear arguments, draw upon scientific evidence, and develop strategies for writing and revising research papers. Class time will also be devoted to developing key writing and research skills, such as structuring academic papers, identifying appropriate sources, interpreting and responding to feedback.

Learning Outcomes

First-Year Writing Seminar (from the VCWC)

- **Formulating an Argument:** Participate in a scholarly conversation by crafting a paper with a clear, well-organized argument and establishing its relevance to the intended audience.
- **Marshalling Evidence:** Identify, evaluate, and accurately represent an understanding of primary and secondary source materials (g. summary, paraphrase, quotation) and show the relevance of those materials to their own arguments.

- **Writing as Process:** Engage various strategies for using writing to analyze and develop their ideas (free-writing, idea-mapping, reverse-outlining, revising, etc.).
- **Academic Integrity:** Distinguish between plagiarism and the responsible use of sources and cite according to disciplinary conventions.
- **Mechanics and Usage:** Formulate their ideas in clear and cogent prose while adhering to rules of grammatical correctness

ANTH-170-05

- Explain how archaeologists collect data in order to learn about people in the past.
- Compare the similarities and differences between life in the prehistoric past and life in the present.
- Critically evaluate how archaeological research is received in the media and popular culture.
- Formulate an archaeological research question and review multiple lines of academic evidence in order to answer the question.

Readings

All assigned readings will be posted as pdfs on Moodle.

Grading

Your grade will be based on four components:

Attendance and participation (30%)	Quizzes (10 %)
Short writing assignments (30%)	Final Research Paper and Presentation (30%)

Grading Structure

Attendance and participation (30%): Every week an attendance sheet will circulate that you are required to sign. It is your responsibility to sign the attendance sheet. If you are not able to do so at the beginning of class, you are responsible for asking for the attendance sheet at the end of class. Full attendance for all 26 sessions of the course will guarantee 15% of this attendance grade. You are allowed one unexcused absence which will not alter your final grade. If you have already missed one class and need to miss another class for emergency reasons, please email me or let me know

However, simply showing up to class is not sufficient to achieve the full 30%. Focused participation in labs or activities, and active participation in group discussions will comprise the remaining 15% of this mark. You will also need to schedule one individual conference with Dr. Beck during Weeks 8 and 9 (Monday, March 23–Friday, April 3) in order to discuss your final paper topic. This will count towards your participation grade.

Short Writing Assignments (30%): This course will incorporate three short writing assignments that are 3–5 pages in length. Short Writing Assignment 1 will be divided into a draft and a final, with each component worth 5%. Short Writing Assignments 2 and 3 will each be worth 10% of your final grade.

Quizzes (10%): There will be five quizzes over the course of the semester. Quizzes will take between 10–15 minutes of time at the beginning of class. These will cover material learned during the preceding sections of class and will vary in format, including multiple choice, short answer, and identification questions.

Final Research Paper (30%): The final research paper will have both a written and a presentation component. The written component consists of a short 1–2 pp. project proposal that will be used to develop an 8–10 pp. research paper that focuses on an archaeological topic of your choice and cites appropriate academic sources. Your topic must be drawn from one of the main categories that will be presented to you during the fifth week of class. You will need to choose a specific project topic and submit your project proposal by Monday, March 23 (the first class after spring break), which will be worth 5% of your grade. Your final paper will be worth 20% of your final grade. It should draw from and properly cite peer-reviewed books and articles, using data outlined in these sources to present a central argument and critically evaluate the research that has been conducted on the topic thus far. During the final week of class, you will prepare a short presentation that summarizes your research for your peers. This final project presentation will be worth 5% of the final grade.

Writing assignments will be submitted by email to jessicabeck@vassar.edu. They are to be submitted by midnight on the due date. For example, the draft of SWA1 must be submitted by midnight on Wednesday, February 12, meaning that you will have all day on February 12 to work on it if you choose. Late assignments will be docked by two points per day.

Plagiarism Policy

In this course you will collaborate with other students during activities and participate in group discussions where other students' ideas will not doubt affect your own. However, in your own worksheets, written assignments, and final presentations, do not submit someone else's words or ideas as your own. Plagiarism will result in a zero on the offending assignment and more egregious cases will incur stronger penalties in accordance with Vassar academic policy. You can read the guidelines on Integrity of Academic Work in the Vassar College Regulations available online here:

<https://deanofthecollege.vassar.edu/documents/college-regulations/VassarCollegeRegulations.pdf>

Vassar College Writing Center

You are encouraged to visit the VCWC at least once over the course of this class in order to receive feedback and advice on your FWS writing assignments.

“The Writing Center provides all Vassar students with a community of experienced peer-readers and writers by offering free, one-to-one consultations at any stage of the writing process—from generating a thesis and structuring an argument to fine-tuning a draft. All students are invited to bring writing projects to the Center, including academic essays from any disciplines, lab reports, creative writing, senior theses, and fellowship statements, as well as resumes, cover letters, and CVs. Students can also bring speaking assignments, including oral and multimedia presentations, poster talks, and teaching plans for leading class discussion.”

More information: <https://ltrc.vassar.edu/writing-center/>

Hours: Sundays-Thursdays: 3:00-11:00pm

Appointments: Make appointments online at <https://vassar.mywconline.com/>

Location: Thompson Memorial Library (Main Library) in Room 122,

Artifacts to Arguments: Deadlines for Writing Assignments and Presentations

Date	Assignment	Length	% Final Grade
Wednesday, 12 Feb.	Short Writing Assignment 1: Draft	3–5 pp.	5%
Wednesday, 04 March	Short Writing Assignment 1: Final	3–5 pp.	5%
Monday, 23 March	Final Research Paper Proposal	1–2 pp.	5%
Wednesday, 01 April	Short Writing Assignment 2	3–5 pp.	10%
Wednesday, 22 April	Short Writing Assignment 3	3–5 pp.	10%
MW, 04–06 May	Final Research Paper Presentations		5%
Wednesday, 06 May	Final Research Paper	8–10 pp.	20%

Please note that during Week 8–9 (23 March–03 April 2020), you must schedule an individual conference with Dr. Beck.

Artifacts to Arguments: Quiz Dates

Date	Quiz	Topic
Monday, 03 February	1	Map of Europe
Monday, 17 February	2	Archaeology & The History of Archaeology in Europe
Monday, 02 March	3	The Paleolithic
Monday, 06 April	4	The Neolithic
Monday, 20 April	5	Mortuary & Bioarchaeology + the Copper Age/EBA

COURSE SCHEDULE

Note: The readings assigned for a particular day should be read **before** that day, to ensure that you are prepared for the lecture, discussion, and activities. I reserve the right to change the readings if I feel it is pertinent to the direction of the course, though in this event readings would be exchanged, rather than added.

Week 1: Introduction

Wednesday, January 22

- **Lecture:** Introduction to course, instructor, and syllabus
- **Activity:** Mapping it out: How well do you know European geography?

Week 2: From artifacts to arguments: Introduction to archaeology

Monday, January 27: What is archaeology?

- **Reading:** Renfrew and Bahn 2018, Chapter 1.

Wednesday, January 29: How do archaeologists make claims about the past?

- **Reading:** Ashmore and Sharer, Ch. 8
- **Review:** Map of Europe

Week 3: Writing Workshop I + Early prehistorians and their impact

Monday, February 3: What Archaeologists Study + Writing Workshop I

- **Reading:** Edwards et al., 2016; Graff and Berkenstein 2006; Lieberman 2019
- **Quiz 1:** Map of Europe

Wednesday, February 5: The history of European prehistory

- **Reading:** Trigger 2006, Chapter 4

Week 4: Who *are* these guys? Neandertals and early “modern” humans

Monday, February 10: Who were the Neanderthals?

- **Reading:** Bahn 1998; Stringer and Davies 2001
- **Video:** Neanderthal (PBS)

Wednesday, February 12: Apples and oranges? Comparing Neanderthals and humans

- **Reading:** Speth 2004

SHORT WRITING ASSIGNMENT 1 DRAFT DUE

Week 5: A hard rock life: Paleolithic material culture

Monday, February 17: What can we learn from lithics?

- **Reading:** Ambrose 2001
- **Quiz 2:** Archaeology & the history of archaeology in Europe
- **Activity:** Flint knapping demonstration

Wednesday, February 19: Paleolithic material culture

- Presentation of topics for Final Research Paper
- **Reading:** Price 2013, Chapter 3 (pp. 56–76; 118–122)

Week 6: You are what you eat: Subsistence in the Paleolithic

Monday, February 24: How do archaeologists reconstruct ancient diets?

- **Reading:** Hastorf 2016, Preface and Chapter 4 (pp. 83-107)

Wednesday, February 27: Hunting and gathering in the Paleolithic

- **Reading:** Grayson & Delpech 2002
- **Activity:** Breaking down a complex academic article
- **Video:** Debunking the Paleo Diet—Christina Warinner

Week 7: Putting down roots: The agricultural revolution

Monday, March 2: The domestication of plants

- **Reading:** Diamond 1987; Larsen 2006
- **Quiz 3:** The Paleolithic
- **Activity:** The Modern Diet

Wednesday, March 4. The domestication of animals

- **Reading:** Redding 2005
- **Activity:** Identifying animal bones
- **Mid-semester feedback distributed**

SHORT WRITING ASSIGNMENT 1 FINAL DUE

SPRING BREAK March 6 – March 22

Week 8: Settling down: Writing Workshop II + Early villages in Europe

Monday March 23: Writing Workshop II

- **Reading:** Savage & Yeh 2019

FINAL RESEARCH PAPER PROPOSAL DUE

Wednesday, March 25: Early villages

- **Reading:** Bogaard et al. 2009

Week 9: Voting with your feet: Neolithic material culture and prehistoric migrations

Monday, March 30: What ceramics can teach us about past cultures

- **Reading:** Holtorf 2002; Loubser 2003
- **Activity:** Collecting data from ceramics

Wednesday, April 01: Prehistoric mobility & migrations in Europe

- **Reading:** Vander Linden 2016

SHORT WRITING ASSIGNMENT 2 DUE

Week 10: Rock & roll: Late prehistoric mortuary practices

Monday April 6: Bioarchaeology: Reconstructing the past using human skeletal remains

- **Reading:** Meyer et al. 2009
- **Quiz 4:** The Neolithic

Wednesday April 8: “The dead don’t bury themselves”

- **Reading:** Parker Pearson 2000, Chapter 6
- **Activity:** Analyzing Mortuary Practices

Week 11: Archaeology & the media + navigating library sources

Monday, April 13: Archaeology and the media

- **Reading:** Finn 2001; Rocks-MacQueen 2014
- **Activity:** Navigating library resources.

Wednesday April 15

- **NO CLASS. RESEARCH DAY FOR FINAL PAPERS.**

Week 12: Pretty metal: The Copper Age & Early Bronze Age

Monday, April 20: Europe during the third millennium BCE

- **Reading:** TBD

Wednesday, April 22: Case Study: The Iberian Copper Age

- **Reading:** Garcia Sanjuán et al. 2013

SHORT WRITING ASSIGNMENT 3 DUE

Week 13: Mean girls? Status and society during the Bronze Age

Monday, April 27: Hierarchy, territoriality and power during the Bronze Age

- **Reading:** Price 2013, Chapter 5
- **Quiz 5:** Mortuary archaeology, bioarchaeology, and the Copper Age

Wednesday, April 29: Case study: The Romanian Early Bronze Age

- **Reading:** Earle et al. 2015

Week 14: Student Presentations and CEQs

Monday, May 4

- Student Presentations, Round I
- CEQs

FINAL RESEARCH PAPER DUE

Image credits: Löwenmensch figurine from Wikimedia Commons/Dagmar Hollmann. Trowel from HiClipart. Neanderthal skull from Wikimedia Commons/DrMikeBaxter. Boxgrove handaxe from Krist Vaesen on ResearchGate. Wheat from dlpng.com. Lascaux panorama from thalo artist community. Neolithic house from <https://blog.stonehenge-stone-circle.co.uk/>. Cardium pottery from <https://forwhattheywerewearing.wordpress.com/>. Newspaper from StickPNG. Megalithic silhouette from CLEANPNG.

READINGS

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